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Study on Laminar Flow by Forced Convection Through a Pipe

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ABSTRACT

There are phenomenon in our surroundings that cannot be fully evaluated efficiently by the mere manual numerical calculations. Fluid dynamics is one of those phenomenon. To fully evaluate the dynamics associated with fluid flowing through a pipe and heat transfer during the process, software based simulation is used. Here COMSOL Multiphysics 3.5a, a simulation software, was used for analysing said phenomenon. In this paper software is basically used to analyse the thermal and hydrodynamic profiles created due to laminar flow of air and water through a pipe using finite element method. Along with these changes in performance parameters along the pipe is also assessed in isoflux condition for the described situation. The final conclusion of the paper signifies that the performance parameters used to evaluate convection heat transfer changes significantly along the pipe due to laminar flow through it.

Key Words: Isoflux, Isothermal, laminar flow, finite element method, performance parameter.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fluid flow inside a pipe is an important heat transfer method. This method is widely used in aerospace, transport & in different engineering applications whenever it's need to quantify the outlet temperature or average surface temperature. It becomes more convenient to real life as isoflux method was used instead of isothermal method in this experiment. In isoflux, heat flux is constant and the surface temperature of the pipe will vary. On the contrary, for isothermal, surface temperature remains constant. For both isothermal and isoflux method, the bulk mean fluid temperature (which is the mean temperature of the inlet and outlet / exit temperature) was considered.

$$T_b = \frac{T_i + T_o}{2}$$

A lot of phenomenon has to be considered to know what will be the actual characteristics of the flow, whether the flow is laminar, turbulent; whether it's in developing or fully developed region; whether the hydrodynamic and thermal entry length is greater or smaller than the pipe length. All these categories need to consider to determine the flow type.

Trombetta [1] examined the effects of eccentricity and curvature radius on the forced heat convection in a fully developed annular flow and considered different boundary conditions. Manglik and Fang [2] investigated the contribution of eccentricity to the heat convection performance through numerical simulation, and their targeted eccentricity ranges from 0 to 0.6. Hosseini et al. [3] studied the natural convective heat transport inside an annulus with different eccentricities. It was found that under the conditions of an adiabatic inner tube and constant heat flux for an outer

tube, the heat transport coefficient increases as the eccentric ratio grows up to 0.5, remains nearly constant until 0.7, and then starts decreasing further beyond 0.7. In another work. Hosseini et al. [4] considered forced heat convection in the same annular channels. Their results indicated that the heat transport coefficient increases as the eccentricity increases. Hussein et al. [5] conducted an experimental study on the heat transport law of the laminar flow at horizontal circular tube inlet sections under natural convection and forced convection conditions. The second boundary condition of constant heat flux density is adopted as the wall boundary condition. The experimental results show that the increase of heat flux density in the inlet section will significantly enhance the heat transport, and the change law of temperature gradient along the flow direction will be similar. The increase in the Re number enhances heat transport both in natural convection and forced convection. In the literature, the position of the mixed convection region was determined by repeated fitting of Re number and heat flux density and determined, and the relationship between the average Nu number and Ra number as well as Re number was determined.

The objective of the experiment was to make a relation by comparing the theoretical and experimental value, the hydrodynamic and thermal boundary layer formation and their characteristics for experiment and theory. Here COMSOL Multiphysics was used for simulation, which will basically solve it for experimental condition. Here, UNHEATED LENGTH was considered for the experiment which means thermal boundary layer won't form from the beginning, it will start to form after exceeding unheated length.

PHYSICAL PROBLEM:

Dimensions: $d=0.01$ m, $L = 2$ m
 For laminar air flow, $Re_D = 2000$,
 $Pr = 0.7284$ (air @ 25°C)
 Entry length check:
 $L_h = 0.05 * d * Re_D = 1$ m;
 $L_t = L_h * Pr = 0.7284$ m
 Inlet condition: u_i (max.) = 3.2132 m/s, $T_i = 20^\circ\text{C} = 293$ K
 Outlet condition: $p = 0$, $dv/dx = 0$
 Wall condition: $u = v = 0$ (no-slip),
 $Q_s = 200$ watt/m²
 $T_o = 30^\circ\text{C}$ [from simulation]
 Then bulk temperature of air is $T_b = (T_i + T_o)/2 = 29.71^\circ\text{C}$
 Thermo-physical properties of air at 25°C
 $\rho = 1.1845$ kg/m³,
 $\mu = 1.8722 * 10^{-5}$ kg/m.s,
 $k = 0.025876$ W/mK,
 $C_p = 1.007 * 10^3$ J/kgK,
 $Pr = 0.7284$

EXPERIMENT:

Fig: Schematic Diagram of Experimental Setup.

Inlet section: .5 m
 Test section: 1.5 m
 ID fan (Induced Duct fan) is used to flow the air through the pipe
 7 thermocouples were placed at an equal interval.
 Multi-meter was used to measure the input power.
 Anemometer was used to measure the velocity of the flow.
 Test section was insulated by asbestos.
 Inclined manometer was used that uses diesel as working fluid.
 Flow resistor was used after the ID fan to somewhat stabilize the flow.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION:

To evaluate the simulation model which is mentioned above, COMSOL Multiphysics is used. This model is associated with convective heat flow and heat transfer. The same model had been built in a laboratory and simulated values were compared with experimental results. A uniform value of length and diameter was maintained throughout the whole experiment. Moreover, air and water are considered as an incompressible and consistently dense fluid. Continuity equation, momentum equation and energy equation are used as governing equations.

Two types of physics from COMSOL Multiphysics are used in this simulation. Incompressible Navier-Stokes is associated with continuity and momentum equation. Conduction-Convection uses energy equation.

Governing equations:

The continuity, momentum and energy equations are used as the governing equations.

These equations are as follows:

Continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0$$

Momentum equation:

$$\rho \left(u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) = - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

Energy equation:

$$\rho C_p \left(u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

Here, density, ρ (kg/m^3); velocity vector, u (m/s);
 Static pressure, p (Pa); dynamic viscosity, μ ($\text{N}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^2$); heat
 conductivity, k $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$.

Fig: Velocity simulation of laminar flow through a pipe (3D)

Number of Degree Of Freedom: 334262

Number of Elements: 48718
Triangular: 48718
Quadrilateral: 0

3. Results and Discussion:

Fig: 3.1

This is a graph that represents temperature change with respect to distance (y-axis). Considering the isoflux condition, temperature profile will vary for every single point on the surface of the pipe. As first 0.5m was unheated, there will be no temperature gradient so a flat temperature profile was found. After 0.5m, due to temperature gradient temperature profile starts to build up and with the increase of length(x- axis) sharp edge temperature profile was found.

Fig: 3.2

This is a graph that represents velocity change with respect to distance (y-axis). Hydrodynamic entry length was 1m. Velocity profile before 1m will vary for every single point on the pipe surface. After exceeding hydrodynamic entry length the velocity profiles will coincide and it won't change with the distance anymore.

Fig: 3.3

This graph represents change of mean (green line) and surface temperature (blue line) with distance (x-axis). For unheated length (0.5m) a straight line was found at the beginning.

Fig: 3.4

This graph represents relation between Reynolds number and Nusselt number as Nu is a function of Re and Pr. Three different l/d ratio were considered.

Fig: 3.5

This graph represents relation between Nu and Re for different Pr number (water and air).

Fig: 3.6

This is a graph that represents temperature change with respect to distance (y-axis) for isothermal condition. As first 0.5m was unheated, there will be no temperature gradient so no temperature profile was found in this region. After 0.5m, due to temperature gradient temperature profile starts to build up and with the increase of length(x- axis) sharp edge temperature profile was found. It's flatter than profile for isoflux condition.

Fig: 3.7

This is a graph that represents velocity change with respect to distance (y-axis). Hydrodynamic entry length was 1m. Velocity profile before 1m will vary for every single point on the pipe surface. After exceeding hydrodynamic entry length the velocity profiles will coincide and it won't change with the distance anymore. It's sharper than profile for isoflux condition.

Fig: 3.8

This graph represents change of mean (green line) and surface temperature (blue line) with distance (x-axis). For unheated length (0.5m) a straight line was found at the beginning. As condition was Isothermal, unlike Isoflux condition straight was found for head region.

Conclusion:

1) The hydrodynamic and thermal profile that forms in the simulation matches the ones that we achieve theoretically.

2) Changes in performance parameters that occurs due to flow of air through the pipe are evaluated by plotting them against one another in different situations

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3. ^aLin Riyia, ^bWang Xiaoqian, ^cXu Weidong, ^dJia Xinfeng, ^eJia Zhiying, ^aChina University of Petroleum, College of Pipeline and Civil Engineering, Qingdao, Shandong, 266580, China, ^bHuaneng Shanxi Low-Carbon Lit., Xi'an, Shanxi, 710054, China, ^cChina University of Petroleum-Beijing, College of Petroleum Engineering, Changping, Beijing, 102249, China Experimental and numerical study on forced convection heat transport in eccentric annular channels